

Mediating Role of Independent and Interdependent Self-construal between Commitment and Marital Adjustment among Married Men

Shrimant L Yadav¹ and Umesh Bharte²

*Independent Researcher, Practicing Psychotherapist (Faculty Minds), Mumbai, Maharashtra¹
Department of Applied Psychology, University of Mumbai, Mumbai, Maharashtra²*

The present study examined marital functioning in Men. The study examined the mediating role of independent and interdependent self-construal in the relationship between marital commitment and marital adjustment among married men. Grounded in the Investment Model by Rusbult (1980) and the Self-construal by Markus and Kitayama (1991) the study examined how and why men stay committed in marriage. The study sought to determine whether culturally defined self-views shape the relationship between commitment and marital adjustment. A sample of Married Men ($N=101$) completed standardised measures of Self-Construal, Marital Commitment, and Dyadic Adjustment dimensions. Correlational analysis supported Hypothesis 1, indicating marital commitment was significantly associated with marital adjustment, while both forms of self-construal displayed differential correlations with various dimensions of marital adjustment and marital commitment. Findings did not support Hypothesis 2; both self-construals, independent and interdependent, did not mediate the association between commitment and adjustment. Commitment is a robust predictor of adjustment.

Keywords: Interdependent self-construal, commitment, marital adjustment, married men

The curiosity to understand how people stay committed drives this study. Multiple studies have endorsed the importance of commitment in long-term relationships. These studies have also established the association between commitment and marital quality. The fear of potential loss in a relationship can influence commitment in people more than rewards (Dutta, 2016). It's been noticed that the management of rewards and costs can shape commitment. Even for men in long-term relationships, commitment maintained the satisfaction and well-being (Hou et al., 2018). Conflict-resolution techniques using effective communication styles helped couples manage demands and conflicts. This influenced commitment and satisfaction (Xu, 2017). Rusbult (1980) created the Investment Model, underscoring the importance of the relationship between commitment and satisfaction for long-term relations. The perceived rewards and costs, comparison levels, and available alternatives mainly determine this. How an individual measures these rewards and costs can depend on their peculiarities. Every individual may align their investment with their apparent rewards and costs. Individual differences in self-sensitivity relative to others can influence these measurements and investments.

Considering these idiosyncrasies, the concept of self-construal was utilised as a mediating variable. Self-concepts in relation to others are the underlying theme in cognitive and emotional processing of relational information. This modulates self-interpreted relationship investments (Kashima et al., 1995). Using this factor, the study aims to understand how self-construal influences the relationship between commitment and marital adjustment.

Marital adjustment can determine the sustainability of long-term relationships. Internal and external factors can influence marital adjustment. How an individual adjusts to and resolves conflicts will define the quality. An individual's internal processing of information about the relationship can be an important factor. Thus, understanding perceptions, driven by idiosyncrasies, beliefs, and self-view, may influence the quality of the relationship. Findings emphasise that perceptual agreement reflects adjustment, and disagreements hint at dysfunction. The agreement or disagreement with partners, based on their self-views rather than their partners', contributes to marital problems (Dwire & Acklin, 2024). Similarly, among older couples, commitment becomes the strongest predictor of adjustment. Commitment displays positive correlation with dyadic adjustment (Clements & Swensen, 2000). Studies with vulnerable populations, such as people with depression, reveal a significant decrease in dyadic adjustment. This was an outcome of difficulties with mutual agreements, emotional intimacy, and healthy shared activities, due to negative interactions (Kannekanti et al., 2021).

Author Note

¹Shrimant L Yadav, Independent Researcher, Practicing Psychotherapist (Faculty Minds), Mumbai, Maharashtra
²Dr. Umesh Bharte, Assistant Professor, Department of Applied Psychology, University of Mumbai, Mumbai, Maharashtra
E-mail: shreemant Yadav@gmail.com

We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Dr. Umesh Bharte, Assistant Professor, Department of Applied Psychology, University of Mumbai, Mumbai, Maharashtra
E-mail: shreemant Yadav@gmail.com

Review of Literature

Investment Model

Rusbult (1980) studies relationships and interactions through the Investment Model. It proposes that rewards and costs, measured against personal expectations and compared with those of others,

define the outcomes in marriage. Individuals feel satisfaction only when outcomes exceed expectations. It is determined by the quality of available alternatives and the magnitude of investments. Commitment increases when rewards are high, costs are low, alternatives are poor, and investments are significant (Rusbult, 1980). It can be assumed that the definitions of rewards and costs are entirely self-perceived, based on egocentric needs. Investments can include time, money, availability, emotional involvement, and self-disclosure. It can also include tangible assets, social networks, the cost of living, and the cost of maintaining a family (Rusbult, 1980). The theory is based on the interdependence theory framework (Kelley & Thibaut, 1978) which emphasises that individuals seek to increase rewards and decrease costs in relationships. Bui et al. (1996) state that perceived rewards have subjective definitions and meanings, and these rewards may be described in terms of how one perceives the quality of partners' intelligence, sexual gratification, and partners' physical attractiveness. On the other hand, costs are experienced through the annoyance of specific traits of the relationship. Costs arise from conflicts, financial costs, partners' inappropriate behaviour, and excessive burden of responsibilities (Bui et al., 1996).

Rusbult et al. (2011) frame the differences between satisfaction and commitment. A positive affective response to rewards exceeding expectations initiates satisfaction. Whereas psychological attachment, sustained orientation with the partner, desire, and willingness to maintain the relationship determine commitment. This study assumed that commitment may become the antecedent of satisfaction. This same assumption energizes the current study to question how one maintains commitment to achieve satisfaction. Research on romantic relationships as an expansion of the investment model provides evidence for intrapsychic functioning. Dutta (2016) explains that communal costs, a desire to make efforts for the partner, accounted for a significant portion of investment variance. Investments in relationships are not made solely through the analysis of rewards and costs, but also through efforts to strengthen them (Dutta, 2016). This functioning can be observed through pro-relationship behaviour leading to emotional rewards. The research sought to examine what maintains this pro-relationship behaviour even in situations of loss. The findings of this study also endorsed the interdependence in couples, by underlining that commitment is a unified global construct, with affective and cognitive processes indistinguishable given the intense cohesion between partners (Dutta, 2016). It can be assumed that some intrapsychic process is activated when evaluating rewards and losses, as well as when sustaining efforts, irrespective of costs. Durmuş and Özbay (2023) argue that subjective experiences and interpretations of forgiveness are significantly related to relationship maintenance within the Investment Model. Perceived forgiveness in couples is associated with greater satisfaction, higher investment, and lower alternative-seeking (Durmuş & Özbay, 2023). Our research contingency is based on a subjective, perceptual view derived from self-construal.

Investment and Self-Construal

Studies highlighting the role of self-construal in romantic relationship accommodation behaviour reveal that both interdependent and independent self-construals are associated with constructive accommodation, characterized by voice and loyalty (Furqan, 2010). In contrast to the assumption that independent self-

construal may engage more in Exit/Neglect relational behaviour. Similar studies examining the role of self-construal reveal that an independent self-construal negatively associates with investment, highlighting the hesitancy of individualistic persons to sustain consistent investments. Conversely, interdependent individuals are positively associated with satisfaction, highlighting readiness to invest and to display social support (Friedman, 2009). Individuals with a relational self-construal have more subjective interpretations of partners' traits, leading to relational strokes, irrespective of partners' transgressions. (Linardatos & Lydon, 2011).

Self-Construal

Self-Construal defines one's self-view and a way of relating to others. How one perceives oneself in relation to others can influence most of their interactions, relations, and outcomes. Research defines two orientations of self-construal: Independent Self-Construal (IndSC) and Interdependent Self-Construal (IntSC) (Markus & Kitayama, 1991). Independent Self-Construal involves an autonomous, self-focused perspective, concerned with personal attributes and goals. It focuses on self-actualisation and differentiation from others (Singelis, 1994; Markus & Kitayama, 1991). In comparison, Interdependent Self-Construal underscores an interconnected self, prioritising relationships and collective aspirations, over self-aspirations and needs (Markus & Kitayama, 1991; Shweder & Bourne, 1984). Self-construal orientation can define differing relating styles, attachments, and priorities. Interdependent self-construal reinforces collective identity within marriages, contributing to commitment and satisfaction (Givertz et al., 2015). Studies report relations between gender and self-construal. Findings highlight gender differences in expression, questioning the belief that men are less social or relational. The gender differences appear as women focus more on couples and relational contexts, while men express in group contexts. Additionally, for wives, the quality of communication clarified the association between commitment and satisfaction (Hou et al., 2018). Interdependent individuals display a preference for sacrifice, compromise, and adapting to sustain a relationship. This commitment enhances interdependence, resulting in rewards (Givertz et al., 2015; Holmes, 1981; Kelley, 1979). Differences in ways of relating in men and women are reported, as women align with empathy and openness, whereas men prefer assertiveness and restraint in large groups (Baumeister & Sommer, 1997). In foreign cultures, this could be due to cultural differences, as men are perceived more independent (Ghosh, 2008), while women often exhibit interdependence through emotional connections with significant others (Ralte, 2017). Individuals with higher scores on Relational Interdependence Self-Construal (RISC) engage in supportive behaviors that are critical in understanding interconnectedness and relationship quality. Findings indicate those with higher scores on RISC experience better relationship quality (Morry & Kito, 2009). Research findings also support that collectively oriented individuals prioritise partners' preferences often at the expense of self-interest (Mattingly et al., 2011).

Marital Adjustment

Married couples bring together their traits to achieve objectives and satisfaction (Burgess & Cottrell, 1939). Locke and Wallace (1959) explained the importance of adjustment to each other's lifestyles in marriages. This adjustment functions through conflict resolutions,

fulfilling expectations, and leisure activities. Adjustment has been studied as a dynamic process influenced by various factors, such as individual differences, stress, and levels of satisfaction. Adjustment can be a tug-of-war between cohesion and conflict, underlined by consensus (Spanier & Cole, 1976). A dyadic investment model is supported by commitment shaped by reciprocal commitments from both partners. It asserts the significance of considering commitment as an interdependent, reciprocal, and mutually constructed process (Coy et al., 2019). Landis et al. (2014) demonstrated that marital satisfaction fully mediated the associations between dyadic commitment and common dyadic coping. Revealing, the more couples are committed, the more satisfaction and thus more dyadic coping. Studies reveal that dedication to a partner is a subdimension that predicts all Dyadic adjustment subscales. Dedication was predicted to be associated with consensus, satisfaction, emotional expression, and commitment, highlighting a peculiar consistency in dedicated efforts towards partners. Also, satisfaction was predicted by dedication, partner welfare concerns, and lower attention to alternatives. In addition, mutual dependence and adjustment significantly contributed to marital satisfaction (Sidhu, 2025). Findings also support mediation by cognitive appraisal between commitment and satisfaction; however, only for wives (Martins et al., 2016). Using the Actor-Partner Interdependence Model, communication was found to be significantly predicting marital adjustment (Kenny et al., 2006). Additionally, dyadic coping enhances relationship quality (Bodenmann & Randall, 2012). Coping strategies have repeatedly shown significant actor and partner effects, highlighting the role of coping strategies in enhancing adjustment (Molgora et al., 2018). This study assumed these coping mechanisms could be influenced by self-view, highlighting subjective and personal effects.

Theoretical Framework

The Investment Model

Rusbult conceptualised the investment model theory. The theory was specifically conceptualised with long-term intimate relationships. The theory is based on the interdependence theory framework (Kelley & Thibaut, 1978), which emphasises that individuals seek to increase rewards and decrease costs in relationships. Rusbult (1980) proposed factors to incorporate into studies of an individual's commitment and investment in a relationship. This is done through studying comparison levels and comparison levels of alternatives for evaluation standards. It attempts to create a structure to predict long-term commitment through investment roles. The framework postulates that individuals in relationships evaluate outcomes in terms of rewards and costs relative to their expectations or comparison level. These evaluations define the satisfaction and commitment in a relationship.

The Self-construal Theory

Self-Construal significantly defines cognition, emotion, and motivation. Markus and Kitayama (1991) explored self-construal and its dynamics, aiming to categorize self-construal beyond the understanding of Western and Asian contexts. The research attempted to understand individuals from an intrapsychic functioning than just from a collectivist or individualistic cultural manifestation. The research empirically categorised explicit and implicit tendencies of individuals. This helps in understanding

individuals from an independent self-focused perspective or an externally formed relational view of self. This view influences the intrapsychic cognitive and psychological functioning. Importantly, their research questions the simplistic understanding of an individual from a cultural perspective.

The theory underlines two categories for understanding self: Independent and Interdependent Self-Construal. Independent Self-Construal defines one as self-focused, driven by self-aspirations, giving importance to autonomy and prioritising self needs and goals, striving to maintain differentiation from others and in relations. An Interdependent Self-Construal defines one as integrated into social and family relations (Markus & Kitayama, 1991). It perceives the self-concept as influenced and functioning through an external view of relations. Their choices, behaviour, and psychological functioning are dominated by adjusting, managing, and maintaining relationships (Markus & Kitayama, 1991).

Rationale of the Study

Studies endorse positive associations between commitment and marital adjustment. High levels of commitment assure investments of various kinds, enhancing satisfaction. The functioning of commitment isn't similar for all couples. Does a cognitive process driven by self-construal have any influence? This examination seems crucial. Self-construal may mediate this link. Commitment may influence an individual's self-view through investments and may enhance marital adjustment. This study aims to examine this connection.

Objectives of the Study

- To examine the relationship between commitment and marital adjustment.
- To examine whether independent and interdependent self-construal mediates the association between commitment and marital adjustment

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H1*: Commitment will be positively associated with Marital Adjustment
- *H2*: Self Construal will significantly mediate the relationship between Commitment and Marital Satisfaction.

Method

Participants

The present study involved married men ($N = 101$) aged 25 to 45 years. They were married in a heterosexual relationship. Inclusion criteria were age and years of marriage of one year or more. The participants were selected using purposive and snowball sampling. Participants volunteered for the survey and were sent a Google Form for easier data collection. The participants were from different socioeconomic and educational backgrounds. These participants were also deliberately chosen from diverse educational, socioeconomic, and professional backgrounds. Participants were self-employed, businessmen, corporate employees, and employees of private firms. All participants were working in a full-time setup. The participants were mainly from Mumbai and other urban areas.

Research Design

The present study employed a quantitative, correlational research

design to examine the association between commitment and marital adjustment, and to assess the mediating role of independent and interdependent self-construal.

Measures

The Investment Model Scale (IMS; Rusbult et al., 1998): This is a theoretically grounded instrument derived from Interdependence Theory (Kelley, 1979; Kelley & Thibaut, 1978; Thibaut & Kelley, 1959) and is designed to assess the four relational constructs that underpin commitment processes: satisfaction level, quality of alternatives, investment size, and commitment level. According to the Investment Model (Rusbult, 1980, 1983) commitment to a relationship emerges from the degree to which individuals experience high satisfaction, perceive poor alternatives, and have substantial investments that would be lost upon dissolution. All items are self-report statements rated on Likert scales: facet items on a 4-point scale (1 = *disagreement* to 4 = *absolute agreement*) and global items on a 9-point scale (0 = *do not agree at all* to 8 = *agree completely*). The scale displays good reliability for the items created to measure each construct. Alphas ranged from .91 to .95 for Commitment Level, .92 to .95 for Satisfaction Level, .82 to .88 for Quality of Alternatives, and .82 to .84 for Investment (Rusbult et al., 1998).

Singelis Self-Construal Scale: The Singelis Self-Construal Scale (1994) was used to measure both independent and interdependent self-construals. The scale contains the original 12 independent items and 12 interdependent items from the original instrument. Additionally, six items were added to improve the scale's internal reliability. Participants responded to questions on a 7-point Likert scale (1=*strongly disagree*, 7=*strongly agree*). Participants receive two scores: one for the independent self and one for the interdependent self. High mean scores indicate high levels of independent and interdependent self-construal, whereas low mean scores indicate low levels of both (Smith, 2009). Singelis (1994) tested the scale's construct validity by comparing Asian-American and European-American groups. Cronbach's alpha for this dissertation study's total 15-item scales has been reported to range from the high .60s to the mid-70s.

DAS- Scale: The Dyadic Adjustment Scale (DAS) was developed by Spanier in 1976. The DAS contains 32 items, presented in mixed response formats including Likert-type ratings, frequency ratings, and yes/no options. The scoring is based on total of all scores, higher the scores higher the adjustment. The scale has four subdomains measuring various aspects of dyadic adjustment, namely, Dyadic Consensus measures agreement between partners on various decisions and choices, Dyadic Satisfaction measures stability and happiness, Dyadic Cohesion measures emotional closeness and shared activities, and Affectional Expression measures affection and sexual relations. In totality, these domains provide a multidimensional understanding of marital/relationship adjustment. Cronbach's alpha for the total DAS is approximately .96, with high internal consistency across the four subscales (Consensus \approx .90, Satisfaction \approx .94, Cohesion \approx .86, Affectional Expression \approx .73). Validity has been supported through significant correlations with other marital satisfaction instruments (construct validity) as well as the scale's consistent ability to distinguish distressed from non-distressed couples (criterion validity).

Procedure and Ethical Considerations

Data were collected through a self-administered online survey using

Google Forms. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study and provided informed consent prior to participation. Participation was voluntary, and anonymity and confidentiality of responses were ensured. Participants retained the right to withdraw at any stage without penalty.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analysed using correlational analysis to examine relationships among variables. Only scores of Marital Commitment and Marital Satisfaction were considered for this study from the Investment Model Scale. Mediation analysis was conducted to assess the indirect effects of independent and interdependent self-construal on the relationship between commitment and marital adjustment.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

All study variables were analysed using descriptive statistics, including independent self-construal, interdependent self-construal, marital commitment, marital satisfaction, dimensions of dyadic adjustment, and overall marital adjustment. The study subjects were 101 married men. Mean, standard deviation, and range observed are shown in Table 1. The sample consisted of 101 married men with a mean age of 37.64 years ($SD = 6.21$). The mean duration of marriage was 9.84 years ($SD = 6.37$). In general, the subjects reported moderate to high levels of marital commitment and adjustment. The scores of both the independent and interdependent self-construals were also relatively high, indicating that the participants had both autonomy-oriented and relational self-views coexisting.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics for Study Variables (N = 101)

Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max
IndSC	76.09	13.92	31	105
IntSC	76.17	14.82	29	105
MSat	42.27	11.59	2	55
MCom	46.09	9.85	17	56
DCon	48.84	12.11	14	65
DSat	24.81	6.61	10	36
DCoh	14.50	5.36	4	24
AE	8.47	2.82	0	12
MA	96.62	22.01	37	134

Note. IndSC = Independent Self-Construal, IntSC = Interdependent Self-Construal, MCom = Marital Commitment, MSat = Marital Satisfaction, DCon = Dyadic Consensus, DSat = Dyadic Satisfaction, DCoh = Dyadic Cohesion, AE = Affectional Expression, MA = Total Dyadic Adjustment.

Normality was assessed using Shapiro-Wilk tests and visual inspection of histograms and Q-Q plots. Shapiro-Wilk tests were statistically significant for several variables, indicating deviations from strict normality. However, the skewness and kurtosis values were within ± 2 , which is acceptable, and the visual inspection indicated that the distributions are approximately standard.

Given the sample size ($N = 101$) and the demanding nature of parametric tests in the presence of moderate non-normality, parametric analyses were still used.

Table 2*Tests of Normality (Shapiro-Wilk)*

Variable	W	p
SCndi	.983	.205
IntSC	.962	.005
MSat	.897	< .001
MCom	.866	< .001
DCon	.946	< .001
DSat	.969	.017
DCoh	.970	.022
AE	.931	< .001
MA	.972	.033

Note. Deviations from normality were addressed through robustness checks and bootstrapping in mediation analyses.

Correlation Analysis

Using Spearman's correlation, the relationships between self-construal, commitment, and marital adjustment variables were analysed. The Spearman rank calculations were also performed, and their correlations revealed a similar trend, thereby strengthening the results.

The correlation of marital commitment was robust and positive, not only with the general adjustment of marriage but also with all the sub-scales of dyadic adjustment. While independent self-construal showed a slight positive association with marriage satisfaction and adjustment, interdependent self-construal was more strongly linked to commitment-related variables.

Table 3*Correlation Matrix of Study Variables*

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
IndSC	-								
IntSC	.14	-							
MSat	.32**	.22*	-						
MCom	.04	.37***	.49***	-					
DCon	.21*	.25*	.59***	.45***	-				
DSat	.22*	.15	.49***	.58***	.40***	-			
DCoh	.18	.07	.57***	.41***	.57***	.45***	-		
AE	.20*	.23*	.59***	.44***	.84***	.38***	.54***	-	
MA	.25*	.23*	.68***	.58***	.92***	.68***	.76***	.84***	-

Note. $p < .05$, $p < .01$, $p < .001$

Mediation Analyses

The PROCESS macro (Model 4) was used, along with 5,000 bootstrap samples, to conduct mediation analyses evaluating self-construal as a mediator in the relationship between marital commitment and adjustment.

Mediation Model 1: Independent Self-Construal: Marital commitment was not a significant predictor of independent self-construal. Independent self-construal was a significant predictor of marital adjustment, but the indirect effect was non-significant

because the bootstrapped confidence interval included zero. Therefore, independent self-construal did not mediate the relationship between commitment and marital adjustment.

Mediation Model 2: Interdependent Self-Construal: Marital commitment was a significant predictor of interdependent self-construal. However, when commitment was controlled, interdependent self-construal did not significantly predict marital adjustment. The indirect effect was non-significant, thus indicating no mediation.

Table 4*Summary of Mediation Analyses (PROCESS Model 4)*

Mediator	Path a (X → M)	Path b (M → Y)	Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (Boot 95% CI)	Mediation
IndSC	ns	$p < .01$	$p < .001$	[-0.09, 0.14]	Not supported
IntSC	$p < .001$	ns	$p < .001$	[-0.17, 0.17]	Not supported

Note. X = Marital Commitment; Y = Marital Adjustment

Summary of Findings of the Study

The current research findings gave partial support to the proposed hypotheses. In line with Hypothesis 1, a positive and significant relationship was found between marital commitment and marital adjustment, suggesting that the higher the commitment, the better the marriage would be across all aspects, such as agreement,

contentment, togetherness, and the expression of love.

However, Hypothesis 2, which stated that self-construal would mediate the relationship between commitment and marital adjustment, was not supported. The self-construal orientations, independent and interdependent, were positively related to particular aspects of marital adjustment, but neither self-construal

significantly mediated the effect of commitment on marital adjustment. Notably, independent self-construal did not differ across levels of commitment, and interdependent self-construal did not predict marital adjustment when commitment level was controlled.

These findings indicate that marital commitment mainly affects marital adjustment through direct relational processes rather than through self-construal-dependent intrapsychic processes, thus refining the theoretical understanding of commitment in marital relationships.

Discussion

The findings reveal strong support for Marital Commitment as an important variable in understanding marital functioning. Marital Commitment displayed positive correlations with all subdomains of dyadic adjustment, namely, satisfaction, agreement, emotional closeness, and affectionate expression. The commitment variable also showed a positive association with the overall dyadic adjustment. These findings are in line with earlier findings, wherein commitment is shown to have associations with emotional, moral, and behavioural functioning instead of just being a cognitive process (Ramirez, 2008). Findings related to commitment emphasise that it's maintained through consistent, repeated investments in marriage and long-term relationships, as well as through support and reassurance (Weigel et al., 2020). As individuals in marriage may struggle with varied challenges and conflicts, commitment can help them sustain through these troubles. Through commitment, one can tolerate multiple challenges rather than quit the relationship. From the above findings, we can consider commitment as an antecedent to marital adjustment and enhanced quality. Commitment can positively influence efforts to create intimacy and closeness, adjust and compromise, acceptance, and letting go. Commitment has also been shown to promote conflict-resolution processes and overall efforts to maintain healthy relationships (Day & Impett, 2018; Sinclair & Fehr, 2005).

Rusbult (2011) categorises satisfaction as a separate concept from commitment. When psychological attachment is sustained, orientation with the partner, desire, and willingness to maintain the relationship determine commitment. Whereas perceived rewards exceed the expectations from that relationship, satisfaction in investments is experienced. Thus, satisfaction is experienced through the rewards in a relationship. Marital satisfaction displayed significant positive associations with most dyadic subdomains. It displayed positive correlations with dyadic consensus, dyadic cohesion, and dyadic satisfaction. Overall dyadic adjustment also showed significant positive relations. Previous research emphasizes satisfaction achieved through affective expression and adjustment as outcomes of the relational system rather than as isolated functioning variables (Gündoğdu, 2007; Kurşuncu & Sümer, 2023). In support of the findings, past longitudinal research suggests satisfaction evolves gradually through dyadic framing of the relationship and a shared perspective of meaning-making (Ouellet-Courtois et al., 2022).

The study aimed to understand the possible correlations and mediating role of self-construal between commitment and adjustment in marriages. It was found that independent and interdependent self-construals were positively associated with specific aspects of marital functioning. Independent self-construal displayed positive correlations with marital satisfaction. It showed correlations with dyadic agreement, dyadic satisfaction, and

affectionate expression. In the case of dyadic adjustment, it showed an overall positive correlation. This conclusion could be a manifestation of autonomy, freedom of choice, and prioritising the self, associated with independent self-construal. Individuals may manage life efficiently through goal attainment, self-growth, and general control over their functioning. This may help maintain a sense of individuality in a dyadic existence of marriage. This satisfaction with identity needs can also enhance marital satisfaction and adjustment. For the study sample of married men, maintaining individuality seems important. This individuality could give them an assertive stance to communicate and express their needs. This clarity can foster control over functioning, inducing satisfaction. The finding aligns with prior research; wherein independent self-construal actively participates in relationships through engagement and communication rather than withdrawing. This participation is voluntary, instead of being a compulsion. Adding to the perceived dyadic adjustment and satisfaction (Sinclair & Fehr, 2005).

On the contrary, there was no association between independent self-construal and marital commitment and dyadic cohesion. This could be an outcome of a necessity for the independent self-construal to maintain a differentiated identity. Consistent with prior research, commitment for independent entities is seen as personal and driven by choice; it's motivated by satisfaction and promotion of personal goals rather than moral perspectives (Ramirez, 2008; Guzley et al., 1998). As men focus on maintaining a differentiated identity in marriage, dyadic cohesion can be hindered. Similarly, commitment can be influenced through prioritising personal goals. It could be because for men, independence supports marital functioning, but may not be through cohesion. Aligning with this finding, autonomy has been found to operate mainly through particular self-definition, which improves individuals' self-other agreement and overall dyadic functioning (Dwire & Acklin, 2024). From a different perspective, men high in independent self-construal may be invested or committed in a relationship only if their individual space and goal achievements are fulfilled.

Interdependent self-construal displayed significant associations with marital satisfaction, consensus, and affectionate expression. It also showed a significant association with overall dyadic adjustment. The most prominent association was with marital commitment. This finding clarifies that married men with relational self-view exhibit commitment as a responsibility, through consistent investment (Day & Impett, 2018; Ramirez, 2008). The findings exhibit an understanding of relational functioning through fusion and commitment to achieve and maintain adjustment. This aligns with prior research stating interdependents remain invested and committed regardless of relational outcomes. Even when relational outcomes change, they display a sense of obligation, role continuity, and belonging rather than a differentiated existence (Guzley et al., 1998). Interdependents derive their sense of identity through intimate connections, by increasing relational involvement and partners' inclusion in the self (Cross et al., 2000). Additionally, sustained supportive actions and emotional involvement that foster adjustment and happiness are linked to this relational orientation (Morry, 2009).

The study aimed to understand the role of independent and interdependent self-construal as a mediator to explain the relation between marital commitment and dyadic adjustment. Findings reveal that neither self-construal mediates the relation. In the case of independent self-construal, it's not predicted by commitment. It

explains that commitment does not induce independent self-construal, and the relation with adjustment is not mediated. This could be because independent self-construal is a fairly consistent trait and not activated through commitment. This could also be due to self-construal being an internal self-view that is maintained as a core belief. This core functioning is stable. Commitment does not predict independent self-construal; however, independent self-construal significantly predicts dyadic adjustment. This reveals that independent self-construal relates to and maintains dyadic adjustment through various ways of self-growth and relational functioning. These results are supported by previous definitions of self-construal as a relatively stable definition of self that impacts engagement in relationships but not through processes such as commitment (Cross et al., 2000; Yang, 2017). Another perspective indicates commitment mostly affects dyadic adjustment through everyday behaviors and communication patterns, rather than through changes in identity or self-view. Rather, commitment is sustained through regular acts of relationship maintenance (Ramirez, 2008; Weigel et al., 2020).

On the other hand, interdependent self-construal was significantly predicted by marital commitment. Contrary to the assumption, interdependent self-construal did not predict dyadic adjustment. When commitment was controlled, it did not mediate dyadic adjustment. The results reveal a direct relation between commitment and dyadic adjustment. Evidence for a direct relation between commitment and adjustment reveals effects of behaviour, cognition, and motivation in sustaining the relation even during conflicts and challenges (Ramirez, 2008; Weigel et al., 2020). The study aligns with earlier findings that assert commitment as a strong predictor of dyadic adjustment and a contributing variable to sustaining relationships (Ouellet-Courtois et al., 2022).

The absence of independent and interdependent self-construal as a mediator reveals that self-construal functions like a distinct personal orientation and is not influenced by commitment. Self-construal signifies a fairly stable sense of self-view and identity that develops over the years. It's a self-concept derived from reinforcement, socialization, and identity-consistent decisions. Rather than being created or activated from any particular relationship experiences (Cross et al., 2000; Giri, 2015). The self-concept is a consequence resulting from collectively creating a sense of self. This self-orientation cannot be altered through external factors (Yang, 2017). Self-orientation may remain consistent through various experiences. Also, for some participants, self-construal may not be clearly demarcated as a binary way of functioning, in which they may see themselves as both independent and interdependent.

Conclusion

Commitment is a direct and stable factor in marital adjustment. Self-construals are important correlates, but not mechanisms of adjustment. Self-construal is not a link or transmission process between commitment and adjustment; it is a self-orientation concept. In our understanding, self-construal reflects relatively stable and consistent self-concepts and orientations. These do not fluctuate often. In comparison, commitment can be associated with relational attitudes. Its effect on marital adjustment is more direct than it is through shifts in self-concept. Future studies should focus on models that use self-construal as a moderating variable.

References

- Baumeister, R. F., & Sommer, K. L. (1997). What do men want? Gender differences and two spheres of belongingness: Comment on cross and Madson (1997). *Psychological Bulletin*, 122(1), 38-44. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.122.1.38>.
- Bodenmann, G., & Randall, A. K. (2012). Common factors in the enhancement of dyadic coping. *Behavior Therapy*, 43(1), 88-98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.beth.2011.04.003>.
- Bui, K. V. T., Peplau, L. A., & Hill, C. T. (1996). Testing the Rusbult Model of relationship commitment and stability in a 15-year study of heterosexual couples. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 22(12), 1244-1257. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01461672962212005>.
- Burgess, E. W., & Cottrell, L. S., Jr. (1939). *Predicting success or failure in marriage*. Prentice-Hall.
- Clements, R., & Swensen, C. H. (2000). Commitment to one's spouse as a predictor of marital quality among older couples. *Current Psychology*, 19(2), 110-119. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-000-1007-7>.
- Coy, A. E., Davis, J. L., Green, J. D., & Etcheverry, P. E. (2019). A dyadic model of investments: Partner effects on commitment. *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships*, 36(11-12), 3471-3491. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0265407518822783>.
- Cross, S. E., Bacon, P. L., & Morris, M. L. (2000). The relational-interdependent self-construal and relationships. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 78(4), 791. DOI: 10.1037/0022-3514.78.4.791.
- Day, L. C., & Impett, E. A. (2018). Giving when it costs: How interdependent self-construal shapes willingness to sacrifice and satisfaction with sacrifice in romantic relationships. *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships*, 35(5), 722-742. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0265407517694965>.
- Durmuş, E. E., & Özbay, Y. (2023). Dyadic assessment of perceived partner forgiveness and relationship investment model in Turkish romantic couples. *Turkish Psychological Counseling and Guidance Journal*, 13(70), 273-286. <https://doi.org/10.17066/tpdrd.1213917.1>.
- Dutta, N. M. (2016). *Romantic relationship investment and commitment: An expansion of the Investment Model conceptualization* (Doctoral dissertation, Auburn University).
- Friedman, M. D. (2009). *Adult attachment and self-construal: A cross-cultural analysis* (Doctoral dissertation, Texas A&M University).
- Furqan, F. (2010). *Accommodation in romantic relationships: The role of self-construal, attachment style, commitment levels, and ego-depletion*. These Digitization Projects. 3810. <https://scholarworks.lib.csusb.edu/etd-project/3810>.
- Ghosh, A. (2008). Transactive memory, self-construal, and subjective well-being in a group of Indian couples. *Interpersona: An International Journal*, 2(2), 173-192. <https://doi.org/10.5964/ijpr.v2i2.24>.
- Giri, R. S. (2015). Culture and self: Gender differences in self-construal. *EduCare*, 9(15), 75-82.
- Givertz, M., Segrin, C., & Woszidlo, A. (2015). Direct and indirect effects of commitment on interdependence and satisfaction in married couples. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 30(2), 214-220. DOI: 10.1037/fam0000174.
- Gündoğdu, A. (2007). *Relationship between self-construals and marital quality* (Master's thesis, Middle East Technical University (Turkey)).
- Guzley, R. M., Araki, F., & Chalmers, L. E. (1998). Cross-cultural perspectives of commitment: Individualism and collectivism as a framework for conceptualization. *Southern Communication Journal*, 64(1), 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10417949809373114>.
- Holmes, J. G. (1981). The exchange process in close relationships: Microbehavior and macromotives. In M. L. Lerner and S. C. Lerner (Eds.), *The justice motive in social behaviour: Adapting to times of scarcity and change* (pp. 261-284). Boston, MA: Springer US. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-0429-4_12.
- Hou, Y., Jiang, F., & Wang, X. (2018). Marital commitment, communication, and marital satisfaction: An analysis based on the actor-partner interdependence model. *International Journal of Psychology*, 54(3), 369-376. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijop.12473>.
- Kannekanti, P., Bhattacharjee, D., Ram, D., & Pachori, H. (2021). Dyadic adjustment and marital communication of persons with depression. *Open Journal of Psychiatry and Allied Sciences*, 12(2), 115-119. <https://doi.org/10.5958/2394-2061.2021.00025.2>.
- Kashima, Y., Yamaguchi, S., Kim, U., Choi, S. C., Gelfand, M. J., & Yuki, M. (1995). Culture, gender, and self: A perspective from individualism-collectivism research. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 69(5), 925-937. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.69.5.925>.
- Kelley, H. H. (1979). *Personal relationships: Their structures and processes*. Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Kelley, H. H., & Thibaut, J. W. (1978). *Interpersonal relations: A theory of interdependence*. New York: Wiley.

- Kenny, D. A., Kashy, D. A., & Cook, W. L. (2006). *Dyadic data analysis*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Kurşuncu, M. A., & Sümer, Z. H. (2023). Nuclear family emotional functioning and marital satisfaction: The cultural lens of self-construal. *The American Journal of Family Therapy*, 51(4), 440-459. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01926187.2021.1992804>
- Landis, M., Bodenmann, G., Bradbury, T. N., Brandstätter, V., Peter-Wight, M., Backes, S., Sutter-Stickel, D., & Nussbeck, F. W. (2014). Commitment and dyadic coping in long-term relationships. *GeroPsych*, 27(4), 139-149. <https://doi.org/10.1024/1662-9647/a000112>.
- Linardatos, L., & Lydon, J. E. (2011). A little reminder is all it takes: The effects of priming and relational self-construal on responses to partner transgressions. *Self and Identity*, 10(1), 85-100. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15298861003633736>
- Locke, H. J., & Wallace, K. M. (1959). Short marital-adjustment and prediction tests: Their reliability and validity. *Marriage and Family Living*, 21(3), 251-255. <https://doi.org/10.2307/348022>.
- Markus, H. R., & Kitayama, S. (1991). Culture and the self: Implications for cognition, emotion, and motivation. *Psychological Review*, 98, 224-253.
- Martins, T. C., Canavarro, M. C., & Moreira, H. (2016). Adult attachment and dyadic adjustment: The mediating role of shame. *The Journal of Psychology*, 150(5), 560-575. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223980.2015.1114461>
- Mattingly, B. A., Oswald, D. L., & Clark, E. M. (2011). An examination of relational-interdependent self-construal, communal strength, and pro-relationship behaviors in friendships. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 50(8), 1243-1248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2011.02.018>.
- Molgora, S., Acquati, C., Fenaroli, V., & Saita, E. (2018). Dyadic coping and marital adjustment during pregnancy: A cross-sectional study of Italian couples expecting their first child. *International Journal of Psychology*, 54(2), 277-285. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijop.12476>
- Morry, M. M. (2009). Relationship-supportive behaviors, friendship functions, and relationship quality: The role of relational-interdependent self-construal. *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships*, 26(7), 843-864. <https://doi.org/10.3200/SOC149.3.305-322>
- Morry, M. M., & Kito, M. (2009). Relational-interdependent self-construal as a predictor of relationship quality: The mediating roles of one's own behaviors and perceptions of the fulfilment of friendship functions. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 149(3), 305-322. <https://doi.org/10.3200/SOC149.3.305-322>.
- Ouellet-Courtois, C., Gravel, C., & Gouin, J. (2022). A longitudinal study of "we-talk" as a predictor of marital satisfaction. *Personal Relationships*, 30(1), 314-331. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pere.12463>.
- Ralte, R. Z. (2017). *Self-construal as related to behavioural regulations and well-being in the Mizo* [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Mizoram University, Mizoram, India.
- Ramirez, A. (2008). An examination of the tripartite approach to commitment: An Actor-Partner Interdependence Model Analysis of the effect of relational maintenance behavior. *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships*, 25(6), 943-965. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0265407508100309>.
- Rusbult, C. E. (1980). Commitment and satisfaction in romantic associations: A test of the investment model. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 16(2), 172-186. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1031\(80\)90007-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1031(80)90007-4).
- Rusbult, C. E. (1983). A longitudinal test of the investment model: The development (& deterioration) of satisfaction and commitment in heterosexual involvements. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 45(1), 101. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0022-3514.45.1.101>.
- Rusbult, C. E., Agnew, C., & Arriaga, X. (2011). The investment model of commitment processes. *Department of Psychological Sciences Faculty Publications*, 26. <http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/psychpubs/26>.
- Rusbult, C. E., Martz, J. M., & Agnew, C. R. (1998). The investment model scale: Measuring commitment level, satisfaction level, quality of alternatives, and investment size. *Personal Relationships*, 5(4), 357-387. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-6811.1998.tb00177.x>.
- Shweder, R. A., & Bourne, E. J. (1984). Does the concept of the person vary cross-culturally? In R. A. Shweder and R. A. LeVine (Eds.), *Culture theory: Essays on mind, self, and emotion* (pp. 158-199). Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
- Sidhu, M. H. (2025). Attachment Styles, Gratitude, Forgiveness & Dyadic Adjustment as Predictors of Marital Satisfaction. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 13, 1. <http://ijip.in/articles/dyadic-adjustment/>.
- Sinclair, L., & Fehr, B. (2005). Voice versus loyalty: Self-construals and responses to dissatisfaction in romantic relationships. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 41(3), 298-304. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jesp.2004.06.004>.
- Singelis, T. M. (1994). The measurement of independent and interdependent self-construals. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 20, 580-591. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167294205014>.
- Smith, M. B. (2009). *Psychological well-being and self-construal among Asian international students: The effect of frame switching* [Doctoral dissertation, Fordham University]. ProQuest Dissertations & Theses.
- Spanier, G. B. (1989). *Dyadic adjustment scale*. North Tonawanda, NY: Multi-Health Systems.
- Spanier, G. B., & Cole, C. L. (1976). Toward clarification and investigation of marital adjustment. *International Journal of Sociology of the Family*, 6(1), 121-146. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23027977>.
- Thibaut, J. W., & Kelley, H. H. (1959). *The social psychology of groups*. New York: Wiley.
- Weigel, D. J., Etopio, A. L., Shrout, M. R., & Evans, W. P. (2020). The everyday communication of commitment: Testing an integrated model of self-construal, cognition, affect, motivation and communication. *Western Journal of Communication*, 84(4), 499-520. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10570314.2020.1739324>.
- Xu, H. (2017). Factors affecting marital satisfaction among Chinese newlyweds. *Journal of Psychology and Psychotherapy*, 7(6), 1-4. DOI: 10.4172/2161-0487.1000330.
- Yang, S. (2017). *Multidimensional self-construals: Testing the structure, measurement, and cultural variability of self-construals* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Sussex (United Kingdom)).

Received December 17, 2025

Revision received December 30, 2025

Accepted January 3, 2026